

Research

Seroprevalence of Transfusion – Transmissible Infections (T.T.Is) among prospective blood donors in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria

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Abstract: Blood transfusion is an effective treatment for saving millions of lives worldwide each year. But unsafe blood has the potential to transmit adverse of infections to blood recipients. This study was therefore aimed at investigating the seroprevalence of transfusion – transmitted infections (TTIs) among prospective blood donors in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria. A total of 400 apparently healthy young prospective donors within the age range of 17 – 30 years and of both sexes were recruited for this study. The prospective blood donors were screened for HIV I & II, HBV, HCV and VDRL using Determine HIV 1/2 (Alere Medical Co Ltd, Chiba, Japan), Diaspot one step hepatitis B surface antigen (Diaspot Diagnostics Inc., U.S.A.), Diaspot one step hepatitis C virus (Diaspot Diagnostics Inc., U.S.A.), and Diaspot one step VDRL (Diaspot Diagnostics Inc., U.S.A.) test kits respectively. From the results obtained, the overall seroprevalence of TTIs in the study area was 10.5%. Distribution of TTIs according to HIV I & II, HBsAg, HCV and VDRL were 1%, 7%, 1.5% and 1% respectively. Sex-wise distribution revealed that more females were infected with HBV and HCV compared to males. With respect to TTIs distribution and age, TTIs were variably affected by age. In conclusion, the results of this study though relatively low compared to earlier studies in Nigeria emphasizes the urgent need for all stakeholders to ensure that WHO's blood donor screening algorithm is strictly adhered to with a view of promoting blood safety in the study area.

Keywords: Transfusion – Transmitted Infections, Prospective, Blood, Donors, Seroprevalence

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Introduction

Human blood is the most donated tissue in medical practice and the ability to transfuse blood and its components is regarded as one of the great advances in modern medicine [1]. Blood transfusion is an effective treatment for saving millions of lives worldwide each year [2]. But unsafe blood has the potential to transmit a diverse of infections to blood recipients [3]. Transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) are infections resulting from the introduction of a pathogen into a person through blood transfusion [3]. TTIs can be transmitted from one infected individual to another during delivery, by unprotected sex and by sharing needles [2]. TTIs are human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV) and syphilis, because of their prolonged viraemia and carrier or latent state [4]. World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that at a minimum, screening of all blood donations should be mandatory for the following infections and using the following markers [5]:

- HIV-I and HIV-II: Screening for either a combination of HIV antigen – antibody or HIV antibodies
- Hepatitis B: Screening for hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg)
- Hepatitis C: Screening for either a combination of HCV antigen-antibody or HCV antibodies
- Syphilis (*Treponema pallidum pallidum*): Screening for specific treponemal antibodies

Voluntary non-remunerated blood donor was defined as a person who gives blood on his or her own free will and receives no payment, either in the form of cash or in kind [6]. An adequate and reliable supply of safe blood can be assured by a stable base of regular, voluntary, unpaid donors. According to WHO, the donors are also the safest group of donors as the prevalence of blood-borne infections is low among this group [7]. In every country of the world, undergraduate students constitute a huge portion of the group of voluntary unpaid blood donors [8]. The World Health Organization is of the opinion that more young people donate blood in low - and middle - income countries than in high – income countries [9]. This has informed the decision of the World Health Organization in encouraging countries in the world to focus on young generation in-order to achieve 100% voluntary unpaid blood donors [10]. As a way of recognizing voluntary blood donors, the World Health Assembly officially designated the 14th day of June every year as World Blood Donor day [8]. This day has been used to encourage more people to become regular blood donors. Based on the relevance of blood to human life, motivation, recruitment and retention of voluntary blood donors are important to achieve safe blood as they are considered to be safest source [11].

Transfusion-transmissible infections remain one of the most serious complications of blood transfusion [12]. Blood safety remains a public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa owing to inadequacies of national blood transfusion policies and services, appropriate infrastructures, qualified personnel and financial resources [13]. Establishing the seroprevalence of TTIs among prospective blood donors is important to informing the direction of prevention and control strategies. Also, the study of TTIs among blood donors is of paramount importance to evaluate the burden and risk factors for TTIs in the general population [14]. Furthermore, the prevalence of TTIs among blood donors varies across the world as well as within countries [2]. This study was therefore aimed at investigating seroprevalence of transfusion-transmissible infections among prospective blood donors in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria.

Research Methodology

Study Area: This study was carried out in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. Ekpoma the administrative headquarters of Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria, has a land area of 923 square kilometers. The area lies between latitudes 6°43' and 6°45' North of the Equator and longitudes 6°5' and 6°8' East of the Greenwich Meridian. Ekpoma has a population of 170,123 people. Ekpoma is a town in Edo State which falls within the rain forest/savannah transitional zone of south western Nigeria. The town has an official post office and it is the home of Ambrose Alli University [46].

Study Design: This was an institution-based cross-sectional study that was conducted in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria for period of three (3) months. A total of four hundred (400) apparently healthy young prospective

blood donors within the age range of 17 – 30 years and of both sexes were recruited for this study subjects. Data were obtained using a structured questionnaire. The prospective donors were all screened using rapid immunochromatographic kits for HIV-I & II, HBsAg, HCV and syphilis.

Ethical Approval: Ethical clearance was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC registration number: NHREC/12/06/2013) of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. Informed consent was obtained from the subjects before sample collection.

Inclusion criteria: Only apparently healthy prospective blood donors who were physically fit, aged between 17-30 years and of both sexes were recruited for this study.

Exclusion criteria: Individuals that were not physically and medically fit, less than 17 years and above 30 years of age among other health conditions were excluded from this study. Furthermore, subjects with the history of multiple sexual partners and those who have benefitted from hepatitis B vaccination recently among other things were all excluded from this study. In addition, fasting individuals were also excluded.

Blood collection: Three milliliters (3ml) of whole blood was aseptically withdrawn by venepuncture from the antecubital vein using a sterile needle and syringe and dispensed into an EDTA tube. The EDTA sample was spun at 2000 rpm for 5 minutes to separate the whole blood into three layers namely plasma, buffy coat and red blood cells. Using a transfer pipette, the plasma was transferred to a 5ml plain container for HIV I/II test, HBsAg and HCV screening and VDRL test. All the screening tests were performed with little or no delay.

Specimen analysis: HIV serostatus was determined according to Centre for Disease and Prevention (CDC-UMD) HIV rapid testing serial algorithm II guideline [15]. Determine HIV-1/2 kit, an immunochromatographic technique, was the first line kit used. Positive results by “Determine HIV-1/2” kit (Alere Medical Co. Ltd., Chiba, Japan) was confirmed with “Unigold HIV 1/2” (Trinity Biotech Plc., Bray, Ireland), while negative results by “Determine HIV 1/2” ended testing. Disordant results were repeated and finally tested with a tie-breaker Kit-Stat Pak. Final results were considered positive/negative on the basis of the tie-breaker result. All batches of testing were performed with HIV-positive and HIV-negative controls.

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) screening was carried using “Diaspot one step hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) test strips” (Diaspot Diagnostics Inc., U.S.A.). This is a lateral flow chromatographic immunoassay for the qualitative detection of HBsAg in the human plasma at a level equal or higher than 2ng/ml and with a relative sensitivity of 99.0% and a relative specificity of 98.6%.

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) screening was performed using “Diaspot one step hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) test strips (Diaspot Diagnostics Inc., U.S.A.). The HCV one step rapid test is a lateral flow chromatographic immunoassay based on the principle of the double antigen – sandwich technique.

Syphilis screening was carried out using Diaspot one step V.D.R.L. test kits (Diaspot Diagnostics Inc., U.S.A.). The syphilis ultra rapid test is a qualitative membrane strip-based immunoassay for the detection of *Treponema pallidum* (TP) antibodies (IgG and IgM) in whole blood, serum or plasma.

Data analysis: The results obtained in this study were analyzed for statistical significance using simple proportion and Chi-square. Values at $P < 0.05$ were regarded as significant.

Results

The socio-demographic characteristics of prospective blood donors in the study area is shown in table 1. Sex-wise distribution revealed that more males (56.0%) were recruited for the study compared to females (44.0%). Distribution according to age showed that subjects belonging to the age bracket of 24-26 years recorded the highest frequency of 33.5% with the least being 18-20 years (16.0%). With respect to faculties of study, the faculty of Basic Medical Sciences accounted for the highest number of subjects (40%) while the least was Social Sciences (10.5%). The 400 level students were the most recruited subjects (25%) with least being 100 level students (12.0%). Based on religion, Christianity

accounted for 90% of the subjects studied while Muslims recorded 10%. Majority of the subjects were single (95%) with 5% of them being married. In terms of ethnicity, Esan recorded the highest in terms of distribution (75%) while others languages apart from Yoruba and Ibo languages were the least (10%). Based on social habits, 12.5% of the study population were smokers while 14.0% were alcoholics. According to risk factors, unprotected sex was the most predominant (7.5%), followed by scarification marks (5.0%), previous surgery and the least was 2.5% for previous blood transfusion.

Table 2 revealed the distribution of TTIs among prospective blood donors in Ekpoma. A total of 42 subjects tested positive for TTIs representing a 10.5% overall seroprevalence rate. The breakdown of seroprevalence rates of TTIs according to HIV I & II, HBsAg, HCV and VDRL in the study area were 1%, 7%, 1.5% and 1% respectively.

The seroprevalence (overall) of TTIs among prospective blood donors according to sex is summarized in table 3. With respect to HIV I & II infection, both sexes recorded a seroprevalence rate of 0.5% each. Whereas, the female subjects recorded a higher carriage rate of 4.0% compared to their counterparts with respect to HBsAg infection. Similarly, seroprevalence of HCV according to sex revealed that more females were more positive (1.0%) compared to males (0.5%). The positivity rate of VDRL according to gender revealed a 0.5% seroprevalence rate for both sexes. However, there was no statistical difference between TTIs and sex in the study area ($P>0.05$).

The results of the seroprevalence of TTIs based on age are shown in table 4. HIV-I & II – related TTIs recorded a 0% positivity rate in all the age groups. With respect to HBsAg carriage rate, subjects belonging to the age group of 21-23 years recorded the positive rate 0.5% each for HIV I & II and VDRL compared to HBV and HCV that recorded 0%. Subjects in the age bracket of 24-26 years revealed different distribution rates of 0.5%, 3%, 0.5% and 0.5% for HIV-I & II, HBsAg, HCV and VDRL respectively. With respect to subjects in the age group of 27-30 years, HBV and HCV accounted for 4.0% and 1.0% of TTIs seroprevalence rates according to age with HIV-I & II and VDRL recording 0% prevalence. Again, Statistical comparison between age and TTIs did not reveal any statistical significance ($P>0.05$).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the subjects studied

Variables	Categories	Number observed	Frequency (%)
Sex	Male	224	56.0
	Female	176	44.0
Age	18-20 years	64	16.0
	21-23 years	126	31.5
	24-26 years	134	33.5
	27-30 years	76	19.0
Faculties of Study	Basic Medical Sciences	160	40
	Education	80	20
	Natural Sciences	58	14.5
	Management Sciences	60	15
	Social Sciences	42	10.5
Level of Study	100 level	48	12.0
	200 level	94	23.5
	300 level	70	17.5
	400 level	100	25.0

	500 level	88	22.0
Religion	Christian	360	90.0
	Muslim	40	10.0
	Traditional	0	0.00
Marital status	Single	380	95.0
	Married	20	5.0
Ethnicity	Esan	300	75.0
	Yoruba	40	10.0
	Hausa	0	0.00
	Ibo	40	10.0
	Others	20	5.0
Social Habits	Smokers (Yes)	50	12.5
	Alcoholics (Yes)	56	14.0
Risk factors	Unprotected sex	30	7.5
	Previous blood transfusion	10	2.5
	Scarification marks	20	5.0
	Intravenous drug use	0	0.00
	Unsafe injection	0	0.00
	Previous surgery	20	5.0
	No identifiable risk factors	0	0.00

Table 2: Distribution of TTIs among prospective blood donors in Ekpoma

TTIs	Number observed	Frequency(%)
HIV I/II	4	1
HBsAg	28	7
HCV	6	1.5
VDRL	4	1
Total	42	10.5

Table 3: Seroprevalence (Overall) of TTIs among prospective blood donors according to sex

	Male	Female	Total	X ²	p-value
No. screened for HIV I & II, HBsAg, HCV and VDRL	224(56.0%)	176(44.0%)	400		
No. of HIV I & II positive	2(0.5%)	2(0.5%)	04	1.000	0.137
No. of HIV I & II Negative	222(55.5%)	174(43.5%)	396		
No. of HBsAg positive	12(3.0%)	16(4.0%)	28	1.356	0.254

No. of HBsAg Negative	212(53.0%)	160(40.0%)	372		
No. of HCV screened	224(56.0%)	176(44.0%)	400		
No. of HCV positive	2(0.5%)	4(1.0%)	6	0.986	0.366
No. of HCV Negative	222(55.5%)	172(43.0%)	394		
No. of VDRL screened	224(56.0%)	176(44.0%)	400		
No. of VDRL positive	02(0.5%)	02(0.5%)	04	1.000	0.109
No. of VDRL Negative	222(55.5%)	174(43.5%)	396		

Table 4: Seroprevalence (overall) of TTIs with respect to age

	18-20 years	21-23 years	24-26 years	27-30 years	Total	X ²	p- value
No. screened for HIV I & II, HBsAg, HCV and VDRL	64(16.0%)	126(31.5%)	134(33.5%)	76(19.0%)	400		
No. of HIV I & II positive	0(0%)	2(0.5%)	2(0.5%)	0(0%)	4(1.0%)	1.000	0.653
No. of HIV I & II Negative	64(16%)	124(31%)	132(33%)	76(19.0%)	396(99.0%)		
No. of HBsAg positive	0(0%)	0(0%)	12(3.0%)	16(4.0%)	28(7.0%)	1.108	0.305
No. of HBsAg Negative	64(16.0%)	126(31.5%)	122(30.5%)	60(15.0%)	372(93.0%)		
No. of HCV positive	0(0%)	0(0%)	2(0.5%)	4(1.0%)	6(1.5%)	1.086	0.411
No. of HCV Negative	64(16.0%)	126(31.5%)	122(33.0%)	72(18.0%)	394(98.5%)		
No. of VDRL positive	0(0%)	2(0.5%)	2(0.5%)	0(0%)	4(1%)	1.000	0.221
No. of VDRL Negative	64(16.0%)	124(31%)	132(33%)	76(19.0%)	396(99%)		

Discussion

Transfusion transmissible infections (TTIs) such as human immunodeficiency virus (HIV I & II), hepatitis B and C viruses (HBV and HCV) and Treponema pallidum constitute a major challenge for transfusion safety especially in sub-Saharan Africa where these disease are endemic [16] [17] [18]. In our research, the overall seroprevalence of TTIs was 10.5%. This is close to the 11.88% overall seroprevalence rate reported by Otu et al. [19] for TTIs serological markers among blood donors in Abuja, Nigeria. Elsewhere, a study done by Mremi et al. [20] from Tanzania showed that the overall prevalence of TTIs was 10.1% of which the leading was HBV accounting for 5.1%. On the contrary, our finding is much higher than the study carried out in Peshawar, Pakistan by Khan et al. [21] where they found the overall frequency of hepatitis B, hepatitis C and HIV I/II to be 2.338%. Similarly, Kebede et al. [2] in a similar study done in Northeastern Ethiopia reported an overall prevalence rate of 6.25% for the subjects they studied. On the other hand, higher overall seroprevalence rates of 14.96% and 22.7% were reported by Okoroiwu et al. [22] and Daramola et al. [23] in Calabar and Ado Ekiti (Nigeria) respectively. Furthermore, in Southwest Nigeria, Buseri et al. [24] reported an overall seroprevalence rate of 28.8% for prospective donors in a study done in Osogbo town. In general, variation in the total sample size, donor recruitment proportion of volunteers to replacement donors, time period, strength of preliminary screening of donors and factors related to test algorithms used for screening the test kits might be the possible reasons

for the discrepancy in the total seroprevalence of TTIs between various studies [25]. Furthermore, Mremi et al. [20] highlighted differences in health care systems in the different study settings as well as the varying magnitude of risk factors for contracting TTIs in the various settings as some of the reasons.

In this study, the seroprevalence of HIV I & II in the study area was 1.0%. Our findings is in tandem with the earlier reports of Salawu et al. [26] and Daramola et al. [23] who found 0.97% and 1.3% seroprevalence rates in the subjects they studied in Ile-Ife and Ekiti State, Nigeria. Furthermore, Oluwayemisi et al. [27] and Otu et al. [19] had reported seroprevalence rates of 1.4% and 1.45% for HIV-related TTIs in North Central Nigeria. However, a far lower HIV I & II seroprevalence rates have been reported by some authors. For instance, the HIV seroprevalence rates of 0.018%, 0.16% and 0.2% were reported by Khan et al. [21], Zahoor et al. [28] and Kebede et al. [2] respectively. A similar data was also reported by Ahmad et al. [29]. Another study done by Arshad et al. [30] in Krygyzstan revealed an HIV I & II seroprevalence rate of 0.78%. On the contrary, a study done in Nigeria by Buseri et al. [24] and Okoroiwu et al. [22] recorded HIV seroprevalence rates among blood donors to be 3.1% and 4.2% respectively. According to Otu et al. [19], the prevalence of TTIs in donated blood is directly dependent on the prevalence of the TTIs in the general population, the type of blood donation, the effectiveness of blood donor recruitment and selection process. There is a high burden of TTIs in sub-Saharan Africa with the WHO Global Status Report on Blood Safety and Availability (2016) revealing that low-income countries have the highest prevalence of the major TTIs (HIV, HBV, HCV and syphilis) in blood donated for clinical use [31].

The predominance of hepatitis B in blood donors has been reported by various authors [30] [32]. Most countries in Africa have high endemicity for HBV [33]. In the present study, the seroprevalence of HBV in the cohort of intending blood donors was 7% in the study area. Our finding is similar to the previous report of Adegoke et al. [34] who found a seroprevalence rate of 7.5% among the subjects they studied in a tertiary hospital in Nigeria. However, our finding is lower than the earlier reports of 1.0%, 1.56% and 1.6% by Ajugwo et al. [35], Khan et al. [21] and Zahoor et al. [28] respectively. Similar data was also reported by Ahmad et al. [29] in Peshawar, Pakistan. Furthermore, studies done in Krygyzistan, Osogbo (Nigeria), Northeast Ethiopia and Abuja (Nigeria) by Arshad et al. [30], Okoroiwu et al. [22], Kebede et al. [2] and Otu et al. [19] revealed the respective seroprevalence rates of 3.6%, 4.1%, 4.2% and 4.4% for hepatitis B among blood donors. Whereas, other authors such as Babatunde et al. [36], Fasola et al. [37], Daramola et al. [23] and Buseri et al. [24] reported higher seroprevalence rates of 10.0%, 10.6%, 12.0% and 18.6% respectively among the subjects they studied. Factors like differences in sample size, the sensitivity and reliability of viral assay reagents, the category of people studied, geographical location of the study population and their socio-cultural practices might have contributed to the differences reported for HBV infection prevalence in these aforementioned areas [38] [39].

The result obtained in the present study showed a seroprevalence rate of 1.5% for HCV among the subjects studied. This finding is at variance with the earlier studies of Kebede et al. [2], Khan et al. [21], Salawu et al. [26] and Zahoor et al. [28] who found lower HCV seroprevalence rates of 0%, 0.76%, 0.86% and 1.1% respectively. On the contrary, higher seroprevalence rates have been reported for HCV among blood donors by other authors. For example; Arshad et al. [30], Otu et al. [19] and Okoroiwu et al. [22] have reported HCV seroprevalence rates of 3.1%, 3.5% and 3.6% respectively. Furthermore, HCV seroprevalence rates of 6.0% and 6.7% have been reported by Buseri et al. [24] and Daramola et al. [23] respectively. Prevalence of hepatitis C vary from country to country and depends upon a complex interplay of behavioural, environmental and host factors [40]. In general, it is lowest in countries or areas with high standards of living and highest in countries or areas where socio-economic level is lower [41].

Also in this study, the seroprevalence of syphilis among a cohort of blood donors in the study area was 1.0%. Our result is comparable with the findings of Buseri et al. [24] and Kebede et al. [2] who reported syphilis seroprevalence rates of 1.1% and 1.82% respectively. However, our finding contradicted the earlier reports of Otu et al. [19], Daramola et al. [23] and Okoroiwu et al. [22] who found the respective seroprevalence rates of 2.51%, 2.7% and 3.1% among the subjects

they studied. According to Abdella et al. [42] reasons for the discrepancy could be duration of the study, cultural and behavioural differences of the study participants of different countries.

The prevalence of TTIs according to gender was 4.5% for males compared to 6.0% for their female counterparts. The higher prevalence rate recorded for the female subjects contradicted the earlier reports of Kebede et al. [2] who found that 15/24 (62.5%) of the subjects who had TTIs were males while 9/24 (37.5%) were females. Similarly, Okoroiwu et al. [22]'s report also showed a male dominated pool (98.7%) with higher prevalence (4.2%) of transfusion-transmissible infections than in female donors. In the same vein, the frequency of TTIs markers was significantly associated with sex with a higher prevalence reported in male donors [43]. A similar association was also reported in a study conducted at the Jijiga Blood Bank, Eastern Ethiopia where Mohammed and Bekele [32] established seroprevalence rates of 11.6% and 3.8% for males and females respectively. Other authors such as Ataro et al. [44] and Daramola et al. [23] have also reported that an overwhelming majority of prospective donors who had TTIs were males. Quite understandably, almost half (44%) of the subjects we recruited for our study were females therefore paving the way for more females to be screened for TTIs in comparison to other studies where male subjects constituted between 70-98.7% of the subjects they studied.

From the standpoint of age, the seroprevalence of TTIs was highest in the subjects belonging to the age bracket of 27-30 years with a carriage rate of 5.0%, followed by those in the age group of 24-26 years. However, our result disagreed with the earlier reports of Song et al. [4] and Siraj et al. [43] who established that the frequency of TTIs markers was substantially higher in donors above 45 years and in those below 17 years. According to Okwesili et al. [45], the high prevalence of TTIs especially HBV among those age groups could be as a result of the high risk behaviours such as having multiple sexual partners, tattooing, having unprotected sex, intravenous drug abuse and other unhygienic practices involving youths.

In conclusion, the prevalence of TTIs in this study was relatively low compared to studies conducted earlier in Nigeria. This has further buttressed the reason why special focus should be placed on the young generation with the aim of making them the integral part of voluntary, non-remunerated blood donors in our locality because they appear to belong to the low-risk group. Furthermore, the result of this study also emphasizes the urgent need for co-ordinated attempts on the part of all stakeholders to ensure that the WHO's blood donor screening algorithm is strictly adhered to with a view of promoting blood safety in our locality.

Author Contributions:

- o Babatope Isaac O. - Research idea and design, drafted the work and Reviewed the write-up
- o Orukotan Rosannah I. and Ukhurebor Godstime O – Field work, Questionnaire administration, Samples collection and analysis
- o Iyevhobu Kenneth O. - Data analysis

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